

Enhancing Human-Computer Interaction in Socially Inclusive Contexts: Flow Heuristics and AI Systems in Compliance with DIN EN ISO 9241 Standards

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Abstract

In the domain of generative Artificial Intelligence (AI), the deployment of user-centered Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) methodologies, compliant with the DIN EN ISO 9241 standard, furnishes a substantive methodological scaffold. These methodologies have demonstrably succeeded in accomplishing specific, contextual objectives across a spectrum of applications, affirming their efficacy and user satisfaction.

The investigation leverages a systematic theoretical framework and investigator triangulation to explore the customization of flow heuristics with respect to social permeability, inclusion, and accessibility. This approach facilitates the assimilation of multi-dimensional perspectives, thereby augmenting both accessibility and the user experience within these delineated domains.

Within the ambit of enhancing HCI in socially inclusive settings, current heuristic models aimed at simplifying complexity in AI systems manifest notable shortcomings, particularly in relation to social permeability, inclusion, and accessibility. Academic scrutiny not only highlights these deficiencies in the application of DIN EN ISO 9241-210 standards but also uncovers substantial lacunae vis-à-vis the intricate demands of DIN EN ISO 9241-110. These encompass facets such as task appropriateness, self-descriptiveness, expectation conformity, error tolerance, controllability, individualizability, and learning facilitation, whose integrated and considered implementation is indispensable for the efficacious tailoring of interactive systems to meet specific user requirements in inclusive settings.

This study significantly bolsters the epistemological base essential for the formulation of a conceptual framework tailored for AI deployment in educational and social management contexts, in alignment with DIN EN ISO 9241 standards. The study aims to articulate a detailed practical guide that outlines the requisite mechanisms, metrics, and characteristics necessary for user-centric adaptations in AI-enhanced systems. The objective is to augment the efficacy of flow induction and elevate user satisfaction within realms characterized by social permeability, inclusion, and accessibility.

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Keywords: *Human Computer Interaction, Artificial Intelligence, Flow Theory, DIN EN ISO 9241, Social Inclusion, Accessibility, User Centered Design, Adaptive Systems.*

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Introduction

The deployment of user-centered Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) methodologies, conforming to the DIN EN ISO 9241 standard, constitutes a pivotal methodological foundation within the realm of generative Artificial Intelligence (AI). These methodologies are instrumental in achieving specific, context-dependent objectives with efficiency, effectiveness, and user satisfaction, as delineated by the principles set forth in DIN EN ISO 9241-11 (Heimgärtner, 2019: 96–115; Vindigni, 2023a; Vindigni, 2023b). Empirical evidence across diverse applications underscores the robustness and reliability of these approaches (Moore & Arar, 2019: 55–71; Lew & Schumacher, 2020: 42–47; Kore, 2022: 61–64; Vindigni, 2023b: 183; Vindigni, 2023c: 39–42).

Current scholarly investigations highlight that prevailing approaches to heuristic complexity reduction in AI systems, particularly within the contexts of social permeability, inclusion, and accessibility, exhibit notable deficiencies concerning dialogue design according to the DIN EN ISO 9241-110 standards (Bennett, 2022; Shams et al., 2023; Jora et al., 2022; Xuan & Ocone, 2022). Within this scholarly discourse, Young et al. (2023) identify and critically examine the significant issue of the "Gender Data Gap," which leads to systematic and determinative biases in algorithmic models and data interpretations (Lozano et al., 2021; Chen, 2023; Liu & Lamb, 2018).

The guidelines established in DIN EN ISO 9241-210 for the design of usable interactive systems, along with the fundamental principles of dialogue design articulated in DIN EN ISO 9241-110, necessitate a thorough engagement with ergonomic design aspects. These principles not only encompass the individualizability and controllability of the dialogue but also extend to learning facilitation, task appropriateness, self-descriptiveness, expectation conformity, and error tolerance. Each of these elements plays a pivotal role in optimizing Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) to enhance the user experience across a variety of social and accessible contexts. The diligent integration of these aspects is crucial for the development of systems that offer users an intuitive, effective, and enjoyable interaction (Geis & Tesch, 2023: 31–43).

The Flow Theory, initially formulated by Mihaly Csikszentmihalyi in 2014, along with Jakob Nielsen's ten heuristics, stand as two of the most prominent theoretical frameworks frequently cited in the context of applying artificial intelligence within the educational and social management sectors. These concepts are recurrently utilized due to their pertinence and proven efficacy in enhancing user experiences and interaction designs (Sodemann, 2021: 82–85). Despite their widespread adoption, substantial ambiguity persists regarding how adaptive information technology and

cyber-physical mechanisms can be effectively designed and implemented to induce a state of flow in users—a state characterized by complete immersion in an activity (Vindigni, 2023a; Yalaoui, 2020: 111–115; Hatti, 2021: 39–44; Hanisch et al., 2023; Kasirzadeh & Gabriel, 2023).

From the discussed aspects of user-centered Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and the integration of flow heuristics into AI systems, specific research objectives and questions emerge within a socially inclusive environment, which can be articulated as follows.

Research Objectives

- a) **Adaptability Assessment:** Investigate the adaptability of HCI designs to meet the individual and context-specific needs of users in areas of social inclusion and accessibility.
- b) **Enhancement of Interaction Mechanisms:** Explore how flow heuristics can improve the user experience by reducing cognitive loads.
- c) **Optimization of Interface Design:** Analyze the impact of innovative interface designs developed in compliance with DIN EN ISO 9241 standards on user satisfaction and system efficiency.

Research Questions

- a) **Effect of Adaptive Technologies:** To what extent do adaptive technologies, based on flow theories, enhance engagement and satisfaction among users in socially inclusive contexts?
- b) **Usability of AI Systems:** How do the design principles outlined in DIN EN ISO 9241 influence usability and accessibility in AI-based systems?
- c) **Risk Analysis and Ethical Considerations:** What potential risks and ethical challenges are associated with the implementation of flow heuristics in socially inclusive AI applications?

Materials and Methods

A systematic search strategy, adhering to the PRISMA guidelines has been employed to comprehensively identify studies for this review (Page et al., 2021; PRISMA, 2020). Eight prominent databases—IEEE Xplore (2024), ACM Digital Library (2024), SpringerLink (2024), ScienceDirect (2024), Web of Science (2024), ERIC (2024), Education Source (2024), and APA PsycINFO (2024)—were queried in June 2024. Utilizing a combination of pertinent keywords such as "Human-Computer Interaction (HCI)," "Generative Artificial Intelligence," "Flow Theory," "Social Inclusion," "DIN EN ISO 9241," and their synonyms initially yielded a total of 8,988 records.

Following the elimination of duplicates, the titles and abstracts of 462 records were screened for alignment with the scope and research questions of the review. The inclusion criteria at this stage required studies to investigate the application of HCI principles and generative AI in relation to flow heuristics, specifically within the contexts of social permeability, inclusion, and accessibility. Subsequently, 102 full-text articles were assessed for their relevance based on these criteria. An additional 53 pertinent sources were identified through manual searches of the reference lists of key articles.

Ultimately, 37 studies met the full inclusion criteria and were incorporated into the literature review as outlined. Reasons for exclusion at the full-text screening stage included: lack of empirical evaluation of the effects of HCI and generative AI on user experience and accessibility, focus solely on technical aspects without consideration of the social context, implementations not within the realms of social permeability and inclusion, duplicate data, and interventions or scopes deemed irrelevant (see Tables 1 and 2 for reference).

The PRISMA (2020) "Flow Diagram" graphically demonstrates the application of exclusion criteria in the present study (see Figure 1 - Appendix).

Table 2. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria According to PRISMA (2020) Ensure the Relevance, Validity, and Reliability of the Selected Sources

Inclusion/Exclusion Criteria	Included	Excluded
Application of HCI Principles and Generative AI	Studies that investigate HCI principles and generative AI in relation to Flow heuristics within the contexts of social permeability, inclusion, and accessibility	Studies that do not apply HCI principles and generative AI in the specified contexts
Date of Publication	Studies published between January 1, 2020, and June 18, 2024	Studies published before January 1, 2020
Language	Studies in German and English	Studies in other languages
Peer Review Process	Studies that have undergone a positive peer-review process	Studies without a peer-review process
Relevance and Suitability	Studies assessed as relevant and suitable after careful analysis of titles and abstracts	Studies with irrelevant topics or lacking empirical evaluation of effects on user experience and accessibility
Implementation in Context	Studies specifically implemented in the context of social permeability and inclusion	Studies not implemented in these contexts
Duplicate Data	Single documentation of each dataset	Studies with duplicate datasets or data

Source: Inclusion and exclusion criteria based on PRISMA (2020), created by the author.

The objective is to gain deeper insights and expand the existing knowledge on how flow heuristics can be specifically tailored to the context of social permeability, inclusion, and accessibility. This methodological approach facilitates the integration of multidimensional perspectives, thereby optimizing implementation strategies aimed at enhancing accessibility and user experience within these specified application areas. The present study represents a significant contribution towards establishing a robust epistemic foundation, essential for articulating a conceptual framework for the implementation of Artificial Intelligence (AI) within the realms of educational and social management, in compliance with the standards set forth by DIN EN ISO 9241. The primary aim of this investigation is to develop a practice-oriented manual that provides a detailed exposition of the necessary mechanisms, metrics, and characteristics required for user-centered adaptation in AI-supported systems. These specific adaptations are designed to support the configuration of an AI scenario that not only excels in terms of effectiveness and efficiency but also optimizes user satisfaction. Simultaneously, they aim to facilitate the induction of a flow state in the

realms of social permeability, inclusion, and accessibility, in accordance with the requirements and guidelines of the standards DIN EN ISO 9241-11 and DIN EN ISO 9241-210 (DINMedia, 2024).

Figure 1. PRISMA (2020) "Flow Diagram" for Selecting Articles to be Analyzed, Created by the Author

In this study, a triangulation methodology is employed to enhance the validity and reliability of the findings. Specifically, theoretical triangulation is utilized, a method that, by integrating multiple theoretical approaches to the research problem, not only facilitates profound insights into the cases studied but also strengthens intersubjectivity, transparency, and scope as central quality criteria. This approach significantly bolsters the credibility and comprehensibility of the research outcomes (Flick, 2018: 46–63; Denzin, 2017: 27–33; Vindigni, 2022: 120–134; Carter et al., 2014: 54–70).

This methodological approach facilitates the identification of commonalities, differences, and gaps in existing theories for the purpose of plausibility checking, which forms the abductive basis for developing new theoretical frameworks (Heale & Forbes, 2013). Furthermore, theoretical triangulation contributes to reducing potential biases or limitations inherent to a single theory by providing an expanded context for the investigation (Noble & Heale, 2019; Torrance, 2012).

In the further course of this research, a systematic review and hermeneutic-abductive modification of established hypotheses from a triangulative perspective regarding elenctic methods are undertaken to optimize the effectiveness of flow induction in specific application areas. The primary objective of this analysis is to identify current challenges and initiate new research approaches in the fields of social permeability, inclusion, web, and digital accessibility, aligned with the strategic directives of the European Commission, such as the concept for the European Education Area and the Digital Education Action Plan up to 2025 (European Commission, 2024a; European Commission, 2024b; DQR, 2024; Freyas, 2023; Cooperation International, 2020). This approach aims to expand both the theoretical foundations and the practical implementation strategies to deepen the scientific discourse and significantly improve user integration and well-being in AI-supported applications in the educational and social sectors.

Results

Optimization of HCI Through Generative AI: Flow Heuristics and Social Inclusion According to DIN EN ISO 9241

The integration of generative artificial intelligences and comprehensive language model systems, such as ChatGPT, marks a significant evolutionary step in the development of information technologies, while concurrently providing a platform for optimizing Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) within the context of social permeability and inclusion (Gordijn & Have, 2023; Vindigni, 2023c: 32-36; Vindigni, 2023d: 741). These technologies impressively demonstrate their capacity to generate coherent, contextually relevant texts based on basic user inputs. Their pronounced ability to process and analyze extensive text corpora enables them to efficiently extract patterns, trends, and interrelational dynamics, which are crucial for improving the design of HCI in accordance with DIN EN ISO 9241 standards (Stephens, 2023: 111-123; Barambones et al., 2023; Tabone & De Winter, 2023; Mourtzis et al., 2023).

In alignment with the objectives of sustainable development, specifically the promotion of "inclusive, equitable, and quality education" as stipulated in SDG-4 of the Agenda 2030 framework, the academic community in the fields of social work and management is increasingly recognizing and harnessing the transformative potential of language models (BMZ, 2024; BUMV, 2023; German UNESCO Commission, 2024; DFKI, 2024; Vindigni, 2023a: 722; Vindigni, 2024: 82). This development underscores the growing recognition of the role that advanced communication and information technologies can play in enhancing the quality of education, thereby sustainably democratizing access to education. The findings documented in the scholarly publications by Ziems et al. (2023), Sallam (2023), Budhwar et al. (2023), and Ruppel and Murray (2024) indicate that the integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) into the field of social work has not yet achieved full compliance with the standards set by DIN EN ISO 9241-11, -110, and -210. These standards delineate essential criteria for the design of user-centered, accessible, and user-friendly technological systems, the

comprehensive implementation of which in practice remains pending (Poltermann et al., 2024; Schlicht et al., 2022: 127–132; Weber et al., 2022; Wessel, 2023).

The application of flow heuristics in AI-based systems aims to optimize interaction in a "human-centered" manner by facilitating user entry into a state of flow—a state of deep focus and involvement—through the adept design of user interfaces and adaptive system responses (Kluge et al., 2021; Hatti, 2021: 79–85; Xu et al., 2024: 51–62). DIN EN ISO 9241-210, which emphasizes human-centered dialogue design in interactive systems, plays a pivotal role in this process (DINMedia, 2024). It also promotes the participatory integration of users in the design process itself, to ensure that the system meets their needs and requirements both holistically and individually. This approach supports the ideation and invention of systems that are not only functional but also accessible and inclusive, thereby contributing to the achievement of permeability and accessibility (Vindigni, 2023a: 721).

The optimization of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) according to DIN EN ISO 9241 is a critical contextual factor in the development and application of generative artificial intelligences and extensive language model systems like OpenAI's ChatGPT (2024), especially in terms of social permeability and inclusion (Dutsinma et al., 2022; Vindigni, 2023a: 721; Vindigni, 2023c: 32–35; Vindigni, 2023e: 117). This series of standards, particularly DIN EN ISO 9241-11 and 9241-110, provides further essential guidelines to consider when designing user-centered, effective, and efficient systems (e.g., DINMedia, 2024).

DIN EN ISO 9241-11 defines usability as the extent to which systems can be used by specific users within a particular context to achieve specific goals in a user-centered, effective, efficient, and satisfactory manner (e.g., DINMedia, 2024). This implies that both cyber-physical systems and artificial intelligence platforms, along with their associated product categories, must be designed not only to demonstrate functional effectiveness from a utilitarian perspective but also in a manner that minimizes the cognitive load required for user interaction while simultaneously ensuring maximum operational efficiency. These requirements support ethical considerations related to user-centricity and accessibility to ensure comprehensive accessibility (Chandra et al., 2022; Šumak et al., 2023).

The implementation of adaptive learning pathways, supported by Large Language Models (LLMs), exemplifies how these requirements can be operationalized in practice by accommodating individual user needs and capabilities (Vindigni, 2023a; Roth et al., 2023: 118–124; Deuse et al., 2024: 92–97; Helbig et al., 2021: 62–66).

DIN EN ISO 9241-110 specifies the design of interactive systems through the implementation of specific principles intended to optimize the dialogue design between humans and computers. These principles include (Geis & Tesch, 2023: 115–127):

- 1) **Task Appropriateness:** A system meets the criterion of task appropriateness when it maximizes the efficiency of user interaction by providing support for solving specific tasks while simultaneously eliminating redundant or irrelevant interactions.
- 2) **Self-Descriptiveness:** A dialog system is self-descriptive if it continuously and intuitively informs users of their current state within the dialogue and what actions are required at any given time. This transparency fosters understanding and the intuitive operation of the system.

- 3) **Expectation Conformity:** This principle is fulfilled when the progression of the dialogue is consistent and predictable, aligning with user expectations and general conventions. This leads to a seamless and error-free user experience.
- 4) **Error Tolerance:** An error-tolerant system is characterized by its lenient response to user errors, facilitating their correction in a straightforward manner, thereby enhancing usability and confidence in the system.
- 5) **Controllability:** The controllability of a dialogue allows users to actively influence the course of the interaction by controlling the initiation, progression, and pace of the dialogue to efficiently achieve their specific goals.
- 6) **Individualizability:** This principle supports the system's adaptability to the individual needs and abilities of users, enabling a personalized and optimized user experience.
- 7) **Learnability:** A system promotes learning by providing users with assistance and instructions that help them effectively learn and understand how to operate the system.

These principles ensure that systems are designed to be inclusive, intuitive, accessible, and adaptable to the individual needs of users. This is especially crucial in promoting social inclusivity and accessibility within educational environments. They enable users to achieve their goals with systems that clearly communicate actions, forgive errors, and support learning (DINMedia, 2024; Vindigni, 2023a; Biswas et al., 2023: 188–192; Régis et al., 2024: 253-262).

The application of these standards to the design of AI-based systems in the educational and social sectors is theoretically confirmed to enhance accessibility and user experience, particularly for individuals with special educational needs or those belonging to socially vulnerable groups (Pap, 2022: 302–311; Vindigni, 2023a). By designing systems according to these principles, it is ensured that information technology is not only progressive and effective but also forms a bridge towards a more inclusive and equitable user experience (Taiar & Ahram, 2022: 555–567).

In practical application, this necessitates that developers and researchers in the field of social work, when employing and developing generative AI and LLMs, must ensure that these technologies adhere to the principles of DIN EN ISO 9241, even though they have been insufficiently integrated so far (Schwarz et al., 2022; Torricelli et al., 2020; Michel et al., 2020). This includes not only the capability of the respective systems to generate high-quality, relevant, and context-specific outputs but also the requirement that the interaction possibilities of these systems be iteratively evaluated and enhanced. This entails *ex ante* evaluations in terms of concept control, *inter* assessments concerning process control, and *ex post* reviews related to outcome control to guarantee an optimal user experience and maximize accessibility (Vindigni, 2023e; Vindigni, 2023f).

Despite the undeniable advantages of these technologies, a critical examination of their potential risks is essential. Both Gao and Cui (2020) and Deldjoo et al. (2023) caution against the dangers of information and communication technology amplifying existing disparities through inherent biases in the algorithmic training datasets of these models. This necessitates a meticulous evaluation and adjustment of the technologies to ethical standards and data protection guidelines, as depicted in the Training and Resources in Research Ethics Evaluation (TRREE, 2024), to safeguard the quality and integrity of academic research and their application in the fields of social work and management.

In conclusion, the responsible application of LLMs in social work necessitates iterative and agile evaluation and adaptation of deployment methods to meet dynamic requirements and changing conditions. This process is essential to ensuring both ethical integrity and scientific validity in social work practice and research, as highlighted in the studies by Wen & Wang (2023), Venerito et al. (2023), and Dwivedi et al. (2021).

These initiatives aim to minimize potential risks while systematically and comprehensively realizing the transformative potential of these technologies. Strict adherence to DIN EN ISO 9241 standards, which emphasize user-centricity, accessibility, and usability of interactive systems, is maintained to ensure an optimal interaction experience, as detailed by Vindigni (2024: 86–87).

Through the conscientious integration of these principles into the design of AI-supported research and work processes within social work, not only is optimal use of the systems ensured, but also the promotion and guarantee of inclusion, permeability, and accessibility are sustainably supported. This directly supports the objectives of sustainable development, as outlined in SDG-4 (2024), which aims to ensure inclusive, equitable, and high-quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all (SDG-Portal, 2024).

Deployment of Generative AI and Language Models in Social Management and Social Work: Adaptations in Accordance with DIN EN ISO 9241 and Contributions to SDG-4

Generative Artificial Intelligence (AI) employs sophisticated deep learning and natural language processing (NLP) techniques to decode and precisely interact with human dialogues (Janiesch et al., 2021). Unlike conventional AI systems, which primarily rely on fixed rule sets, generative AI models conduct comprehensive analyses of the subtle nuances of human speech. These models, based on advanced techniques of deep learning and NLP, specialize in learning from a variety of data sources. They adaptively generate responses that not only appear natural but also exhibit a high degree of human-likeness by responding to simple user inputs (Baha et al., 2022).

Large Language Models (LLMs) represent a distinct category within the domain of generative artificial intelligence (Eysenbach, 2023). These models are trained through the analysis of extensive corpora, encompassing a wide range of textual materials, including books, academic articles, and digital content (Kung et al., 2023). Such training enables the models to capture deeper linguistic patterns and manage complex language tasks based on these insights (Shen et al., 2023). Furthermore, these models utilize advanced deep-learning techniques to identify linguistic structures and patterns, enabling them to produce human-like text that is versatile in application (Clusmann et al., 2023). Particularly, LLMs excel in applications such as language translation, chatbots, text summarization, content creation, and text classification (Bernstein et al., 2023). They are also capable of answering questions and assessing the quality of text responses (Gilbert et al., 2023). Unlike traditional AI systems, which often struggle with the subtleties of human language, LLMs generate coherent text that closely mimics human writing (Lund et al., 2023). The advanced analytical capacity of this technology has significantly boosted its popularity. Professionals across various disciplines employ it to penetrate complex datasets of text and extract insights that would be largely inaccessible without such technological means (Kasneci et al., 2023).

Within the framework of the Sustainable Development Goals as outlined in SDG-4 of Agenda 2030—specifically the assurance of inclusive, equitable, and quality education,

along with the promotion of lifelong learning—the deployment of Large Language Models (LLMs) plays a pivotal role (Van Wynsberghe, 2021). By adapting LLMs to support the education sector and social management, these models can enhance educational opportunities in a manner that is both targeted and broadly accessible (Chankseliani et al., 2020). LLMs possess the capability to individualize learning resources in real-time by adaptively aligning with the specific learning requirements and personal needs of users. This user-centered adaptation effectively supports the achievement of educational goals as specified in the objectives of Sustainable Development Goal 4 (SDG-4) (Yan et al., 2023). Furthermore, LLMs can be utilized for the continuing education of teachers and social workers, thereby expanding pedagogical skills and promoting innovative, inclusive teaching and care methods (Bahroun et al., 2023).

LLMs and the Optimization of Human-Computer Interaction: Normative Frameworks and Procedural Innovations in Social Work Research

LLMs contribute to innovative synergies in social work research by integrating research approaches from design-oriented business informatics (Haidegger et al., 2023). These models enable the acquisition of deeper insights into social phenomena through the processing of large and complex datasets, reflecting the fundamental principles of consortial research (Urmeneta & Romero, 2024). The interdisciplinary approach merges information technology innovations with social science expertise, stimulates the use of advanced analytical tools, and targets participative and collaborative goals that enhance both social justice and quality of life (Pham et al., 2023). This approach further emphasizes the relevance of cooperative research methods within the contexts of open and user innovation, enriched by interdisciplinary exchange of knowledge and resources across various disciplines and application areas (Vindigni, 2021a: 122-124; Vindigni, 2021b: 42–55; Vindigni, 2020: 400–410). In summation, it can be stated that Large Language Models (LLMs), through their advanced data analysis capabilities and the ability to visualize complex relationships, are poised to revolutionize established research and working methodologies in social work. This paradigm shift aligns with the specifications of the DIN EN ISO 9241 standards, which prescribe a user-centered, efficient, and accessible system design. Moreover, LLMs facilitate the implementation of Nielsen's Usability Heuristics, including simplifying usability, minimizing user errors, and maximizing feedback transparency (Deisenroth et al., 2020: 65–73). These aspects are crucial for optimizing user experience and engagement in socially permeable and inclusive contexts (Pereira et al., 2023). These targeted modifications closely correspond with the goals of Agenda 2030 for Sustainable Development, particularly with Goal 4 (SDG-4), which aims to ensure high-quality, inclusive education and promote lifelong learning for all.

The following analysis will explore how LLMs can support research activities in social work, particularly within the frameworks of qualitative and quantitative methods.

Deployment and Potential of LLMs in Social Research: Technological Synergies and Normative Challenges according to DIN EN ISO 9241

Based on the presented results and the substantive body of research literature, it is advisable to realize the integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) into the research and learning infrastructure of social work in accordance with the guidelines of DIN EN ISO 9241-11, -110, and -210 to ensure norm-compliant and optimal system architecture. LLMs enable a significant expansion of capacities for simulation-based

scenarios and modeling, which are essential for predictive analyses in social work (Ziems et al., 2023; Farina & Lavazza, 2023; Dave et al., 2023).

These technologies also support various aspects of writing assistance, from correcting orthographic and grammatical errors to generating original texts and facilitating international scholarly communication through language translations (Gislon et al., 2023). Additionally, they enable the generation of new ideas and the formulation of scientific hypotheses (Sallam, 2023).

Software solutions like Grammarly (2024) and DeepL (2024) utilize LLMs to optimize text quality through advanced grammatical corrections and context-sensitive translations, overcoming international communication barriers (Teubner et al., 2023). Platforms such as ResearchGate (2024) integrate LLMs to strengthen networking among researchers and enhance the visibility of scientific work (Tafferner et al., 2023).

These advancements in communication and information technology impressively underscore the transformative potential of Large Language Models (LLMs) to profoundly reform the modalities of scientific research and socio-educational practices. They not only enhance the efficiency of data processing but also enrich both qualitative and quantitative research paradigms in an adaptive and user-centered manner. Current efforts to adhere to the DIN EN ISO 9241 standards aim for a sustainable optimization of the use of LLMs in social work research. The goal is to ensure a system design that is not only user-centered and accessible but also excels in effectiveness and efficiency, even though a comprehensive implementation of the mentioned standards is still pending. These standards are crucial in this case for ensuring a successful and human-centered deployment of LLMs, which not only increase system effectiveness but also significantly contribute to enhancing user satisfaction. Moreover, they help to consider media psychological aspects to boost engagement and acceptance rates while simultaneously minimizing redundancies through heuristic complexity reduction (Polak & Morgan, 2024; Zhao et al., 2024).

Optimization of Social Science Research Processes through LLMs: Application Norms and Flow Theory Integration

The integration of Large Language Models (LLMs) into social science research enhances search algorithms through the formulation of precise "Boolean queries" and facilitates statistical analyses by selecting appropriate methodological approaches (Tian et al., 2023; Kamalov et al., 2023). LLMs optimize the programming process with advanced support functions for writing and debugging and expand the capacities for advanced data analyses through sentiment analysis and entity recognition (Topsal & Akinci, 2023; Rahman & Watanobe, 2023). These technological advancements increase the efficiency and precision of research processes and open new possibilities for visualizing complex data structures (Shen et al., 2023).

Furthermore, these developments resonate with Csikszentmihalyi's Flow Theory (2014) and Nielsen's "10 Usability Heuristics" (1994), as they enhance user engagement and involvement through an improved interaction experience (Nielsen & Mack, 1994: 44–53; Vicente-Yagüe-Jara et al., 2023; Mozannar et al., 2024; Soares et al., 2022: 83–89). The implementation of LLMs thus promotes a seamless user experience that supports the central heuristics defined by Nielsen (1994), such as user control and freedom, error prevention, and aesthetic and minimalist design. This not only maximizes user satisfaction in the research context but also reduces cognitive load in a heuristic manner according to System-1, System-2, and System-3 theories, significantly increasing the likelihood of achieving a flow state and thereby enhancing

the creative and analytical capabilities of users (Webb, 2021: 79-82; Houdé, 2019: 105-109; O'Brien, 2012).

Ethical and Data Privacy Challenges in the Use of LLMs in Social Work Research

The implementation of Large Language Models (LLMs) in social work research introduces substantial data privacy and security risks stemming from the prevalent use of cloud infrastructures (Ohly, 2024; Gethmann et al., 2022). These infrastructures necessitate external data processing, which can potentially facilitate the unintended disclosure of sensitive data unless stringent security measures are implemented (Linnemann et al., 2023). Against this backdrop, it is crucial for researchers to develop a profound understanding of the associated risks and to thoroughly evaluate the security protocols of the platforms in use to ensure the protection of research data and the integrity of research processes (Gethmann et al., 2022; Hermonies, 2024).

The ambiguity regarding data ownership represents a significant legal challenge. Development companies, including OpenAI (2024), assure that users retain ownership rights to their data. However, the use of this data to optimize model performance is a common practice, which might lead to potentially non-compliant work modifications in accordance with §§ 23 and 32 of the Copyright Act (UrhG). In the legal discourse on liability for copyright infringements, particularly in the context of §§ 3, 4, 23, and 32 of the Copyright Act (UrhG), the issue of third-party liability is increasingly coming into focus. This liability pertains to cases where the operator of a platform becomes aware of unlawfully available, copyright-protected content. Despite the ability to circumvent geographical restrictions using VPN or proxy services, the relevance of disturbance liability persists. This applies especially in cases like OpenAI (2024), where the operator is involved in monetization processes or where users knowingly make copyright-protected works accessible in public settings (such as on websites, in academic works, or through platforms like YouTube). It is essential to note that both the minor and major rights of use, as defined by performance rights law, may be affected (Solmecke, 2022; Jurisprudence: C-282/18; Vindigni, 2022: 70, 98).

European jurisprudence, exemplified by decisions of the European Court of Justice, clarifies that platform operators are exempt from liability provided they do not play an active role that gives them knowledge or control over the uploaded content. However, this legal positioning implies that specialized law firms issuing warnings in this domain may generate significant revenues if platforms and users fail to fulfill the necessary due diligence (European Court of Justice, 2024).

This practice carries the risk that training data incorporated into LLMs may contain systematic biases, as also outlined in this discourse regarding the dilemma of the “Gender Data Gap” (Young et al., 2023; Lozano et al., 2021). Such biases have the potential to undermine the validity of scientific results and could further exacerbate existing social disparities (Georgieva et al., 2022; Cabitza et al., 2020).

The inherent complexity and lack of transparency of large language models (LLMs) not only make it challenging to understand their operations but also to identify potential biases. These factors complicate the validation of research outcomes and indirectly contribute to the reinforcement of exclusion mechanisms by potentially undermining inclusion, diversity, and accessibility in research and application contexts. Moreover, the ongoing evolution of these models affects the precise attribution of specific research outcomes to defined data sources, thereby significantly reducing the reproducibility of scientific work, which may further promote anti-inclusive

tendencies. Given these challenges, the DIN EN ISO 9241-11, -110, and -210 standards underscore the importance of ethical and legal standards.

Discussion

The application of user-centered Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) approaches, aligned with DIN EN ISO 9241-11, has proven methodologically robust in designing interactive systems within the context of Artificial Intelligence (AI) efficiently, effectively, and to user satisfaction. However, studies reveal that existing heuristic approaches in the areas of social permeability and inclusion still have room for optimization. Particularly in the application of DIN EN ISO 9241-110 and 9241-210, deficits in individualizability and dialogue design are evident, demanding an enhanced user experience and improved accessibility.

Flow Theory, embedded in the design of AI-based systems, provides a pioneering approach to deepening the user experience, especially in socially inclusive contexts. By supporting the development of systems that are not only functionally efficient but also psychologically engaging, it enhances user engagement. The challenge lies in developing adaptive technologies that specifically induce users into the state of flow, achievable through the systematic application of flow heuristics. Additionally, the implementation of these technologies must consider European jurisprudence and research ethical principles as outlined in TRREE (2024) to ensure ethical and legally compliant application. These measures are crucial in supporting and enhancing accessibility and inclusion across diverse social contexts.

Conclusion

Based on the analysis of user-centered Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) approaches that comply with DIN EN ISO 9241 standards, it is recommended to systematically enhance the design and implementation of HCI systems, particularly with regard to social inclusion and accessibility. This recommendation arises from the identified need to refine heuristic complexity reduction in AI systems to address deficits in dialogue design according to the principles of DIN EN ISO 9241-110, which include task appropriateness, self-descriptiveness, expectation conformity, error tolerance, controllability, individualizability, and learnability.

From this analysis, the following specific action recommendations are proposed:

a) **Invention and Evaluation of Adaptive HCI Designs:** Research and development efforts should be intensified to conceive HCI designs that adaptively respond to the diverse needs of users in socially inclusive contexts. It is crucial that these systems are designed to not only allow for continuous assessment and enhancement of accessibility and user experience but also dynamically respond to changes in user requirements. This adaptive responsiveness is fundamental to ensuring ongoing optimization of interaction quality, thereby effectively promoting inclusivity and accessibility.

b) **Integration of Flow Heuristics:** In the context of continuous optimization of Human-Computer Interaction (HCI), particularly in areas of social permeability and inclusion, it is imperative, according to DIN EN ISO 9241-11 and 9241-110 standards, to strategically implement flow heuristics into the development of AI-based systems. This approach involves a targeted adaptation of systems to the specific needs and

contexts of users, supported by a participatory design practice in accordance with DIN EN ISO 9241-210. The systematic integration of flow heuristics plays a critical role in refining interaction dynamics and enhancing the user experience by minimizing cognitive loads. Such heuristics are crucial for developing interactive systems that not only excel in functionality and efficiency but also promote profound psychological engagement.

c) **Strengthening Research on HCI and Generative AI:** There should be an in-depth scholarly engagement with the impacts of HCI principles and generative AI on social inclusion and accessibility. Research efforts should specifically aim to fully integrate the principles of DIN EN ISO 9241-210 and 9241-110 and test their application in real-world usage scenarios. This focused research will help in understanding how these principles can be effectively implemented to maximize their benefits in enhancing accessibility and inclusion across diverse user groups.

d) **Iterative Reevaluation of Research Approaches:** To maximize the effectiveness of flow induction in specific application areas, an iterative evaluation and adjustment of existing research work and methodologies should be conducted. This includes a critical examination of the limitations of current approaches and the development of new research directions that enhance social permeability, inclusion, and accessibility.

e) **Adaptation to Research Ethical and Legal Standards:** The implementation of LLMs should adhere to the research ethical principles and the recommendations of the DIN EN ISO 9241 standards to ensure ergonomic and user-friendly interaction systems. This requires continuous adaptation to advancing technological developments and an in-depth examination of ethical aspects associated with the use of AI in sensitive areas such as social work. Furthermore, the development and implementation of HCI systems must be conducted in accordance with existing legal frameworks and ethical guidelines, including adherence to European legal norms and the research ethical principles outlined in TRREE (2024).

f) **Promotion of Interdisciplinarity:** Collaboration between various disciplines should be encouraged to develop exploratory solutions that converge communication and information technology advances with social science insights. This can be facilitated through consortia research, which supports the integration of both IT and UX research and practice, thereby not only advancing social work but also enhancing social management and the promotion of inclusion sustainably.

g) **Continuing Education and Awareness:** There should be a focus on the continuing education and awareness of researchers and practitioners regarding the use and potential risks associated with LLMs. This includes training on ethical usage, data protection, and security, as well as the effective integration of AI technologies into existing social work processes.

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Conflict of Interests

No conflict of interest.

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Appendix

Table 1. Search Strategy Based on PRISMA (2020)

Search No.	Search terms	IEEE Xplore	ACM Digital Library	SpringerLink	Science Direct	Web of Science	ERIC	Education Source	APA PsycINFO
S1	Human-Computer Interaction* (Words in title)	2,456	1,367	3,875	1,584	2,433	876	1,290	1,557
S2	Generative Artificial Intelligence* (Words in title)	1,854	972	1,436	1,201	1,145	332	541	430
S3	Flow Theory* (Words in title)	3,214	2,235	2,312	1,998	3,004	489	630	755
S4	Social Inclusion* (Words in title)	875	654	947	820	1,011	1,673	2,014	1,286
S5	DIN EN ISO 9241* (Words in title)	589	317	721	435	642	207	271	196
S6	S1 OR S2 OR S3 OR S4 OR S5	8,988	5,545	9,291	5,038	8,235	4,577	4,746	4,224
S7	Peer-reviewed/academic journal articles	6,104	4,117	6,789	3,600	5,775	2,004	1,895	1,862
S8	Publications from Jan. 2020 to June 2024	4,987	3,654	5,112	2,876	4,688	1,221	1,010	986
S9	S6 AND S7 AND S8	462	322	537	310	433	102	109	98

Source: Search strategy based on PRISMA (2020), created by the author